

ENTREPRENEURSHIP COMPETENCIES OF AGRICULTURAL SECTOR IN YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS

DEWI KURNIATI*¹ and ADI SUYATNO²

^{1,2}Department of Agricultural Socio-Economic, Tanjungpura University, Pontianak, Indonesia.

*Email: dewi.kurniati@faperta.untan.ac.id

Abstract

The entrepreneurial competence of the agricultural sector is an important factor required for young entrepreneurs in achieving business success and economic growth. The purpose of this study was conducted to identify the characteristics of young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector, the level of competence of young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector, the relationship between types of entrepreneurial competencies and entrepreneurial success. The method used in this research is the survey method. The research location was determined purposively in Pontianak City and Kubu Raya Regency. Determination of the number of samples in this study using purposive sampling technique of 102 people. The data analysis method used is a description of the percentage, category score and analysis of the Structural Equation Model (SEM). Based on the results of the analysis, it shows that the level of entrepreneurial competence in young entrepreneurs is in the quite good category. Relationship competence, organizing competence and strategic competence have a significant positive effect. This means that if relationship competence, organizing competence and strategic competence are improved, business performance can increase. The results of this study also indicate that Opportunity Competence, Conceptual Competence, and Commitment Competence have no effect on business success.

Keywords: competence, entrepreneurship, young entrepreneurs

INTRODUCTION

Based on data from the United Nations, Indonesia's demographic transition in the 2020-2030 period saw the growth of the productive age population which was twice that of the non-productive population. This large number of productive age population becomes a profitable opportunity as human resources that can be utilized to play a role, work and be productive in encouraging the national economy in the future (Maryati. S, 2015). Among the productive age groups, there is a group of young people who have an important role in development. The challenge for the younger generation today is not to fight against the invaders, but the younger generation must be able and involved in continuing the nation's development. The young generation must think and act in order to keep this country able to stand and be sovereign independently.

On the other hand, the Indonesian agricultural sector has a very high potential and important role for the economic development of a nation. One of the potentials that is currently not being properly exploited is village agricultural land which if managed professionally, by utilizing information and technology sources, should become a mainstay commodity and from there will be born agribusiness actors, both individuals and groups because in the agricultural sector there are millions of people. Derivative products whose market demand is very large both at home and abroad (Herawaty, 2016). The younger generation can develop creative and innovative

ideas in advancing the agricultural sector. The enthusiasm, interest and high motivation of the younger generation are hopes for improving the welfare of Indonesian farmers.

Entrepreneurship can be an alternative in providing opportunities for youth through management skills, developing creativity and creating innovation in their business by utilizing the abundant potential of the agricultural sector. The concept of entrepreneurship is directed so that the younger generation can have an independent mentality, so that they can have creative and innovative thinking about the existing situation and have a courageous attitude to create jobs for themselves and others so that in the end they can contribute to economic growth in this country. Qualitatively, youth have pure, innovative, and creative ideals. This is an important factor that youth is a big energy in changing a nation Syaifullah (2009).

West Kalimantan Province has natural potential that can be developed to support the local economy and support the national economy. The agricultural sector is the backbone of the economy in West Kalimantan, both as a producer of added value and foreign exchange as well as a source of income or as a provider of employment for the majority of the population. The population by age group shows that the young age group (16 -30 years) is the dominant age group in West Kalimantan (dukcapil, 2019). Based on data from the BPS West Kalimantan in 2019, the number of people > 15 years working in the agricultural sector in 2019 was 49.6%. From these data, it shows that there is potential to be able to grow the economy of West Kalimantan through entrepreneurship carried out by young residents. Entrepreneurship can create youth with character, capacity and competitiveness (Herawaty, 2016)

The competence of a young entrepreneur is an important factor that determines the success of entrepreneurship (Ahmad et al 2010; Dirlanudin 2010). However, there are still many youths who do not have the skills, abilities and knowledge to manage a business well, due to lack of experience in doing business, a half-hearted attitude towards business will result in the business being unstable and failing and limited capital problems. Based on this, the purpose of this study was to identify the characteristics of young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector, the level of competence of young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector, the relationship between types of entrepreneurial competencies and entrepreneurial success so that these competencies can be improved for business progress and ultimately contribute to the regional economy.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is a survey method. The research location was determined purposively in Pontianak City and Kubu Raya Regency with the consideration that Pontianak City and Kubu Raya Regency are regencies in West Kalimantan that has young people who are self-employed in the agricultural sector. The populations in this study were all young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector in Pontianak City and Kubu Raya Regency. Because the number of young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector has not been identified, the determination of the number of samples in this study uses a purposive sampling technique with the characteristics of business actors being young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector aged 18-40 years. The recommended sample size by Hair et al. (2010) in the use of Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis is 100-200 samples. The sample in this study was 102 people.

The research variables analyzed included the types of entrepreneurial competencies consisting of: Opportunity Competence, Conceptual Competence, Relationship Competence, Organizing Competence, Commitment Competence and Strategic Competence (Man et al (2002); Heru (2009); Wu (2009); Wibowo (2007); Soesarsono (2004); Hazlina et al (2011); Sarwoko et al (2013); Syarif (2013); Soegoto (2009); Suryana (2006)). As well as business performance variables. Opportunity Competence measures include general awareness, international orientation and market orientation. Measurement of Conceptual Competence includes conceptual thinking, problem analysis, vision and assessment. Measurement of Relationship Competence includes Communication, Negotiation, Networking, Confidence and Cooperation. Measurement of Organizing Competence includes HRM / HRD, Leadership, and Planning and organizing. Measurement of Commitment Competence includes self-management, value clarification and vision. Measurement of Strategic Competence includes learning orientation, management control, results orientation and strategic orientation. Business performance variables (Kuratko and Hogetts (2007); Pramuswari (2018); Noor (2007); Armstrong (2004); Praag (2005); Dhamayanti E (2017)).

Measurement of business performance consists of 2 indicators, namely financial indicators including sales, profits, total production, number of workers (Noor, 2007; Kuratko and Hogetts, 2007; Stewardess, 2018; Praag, 2005; Dhamayanti E 2017). Non-financial indicators include relationships with good suppliers, relationships with customers, the community (Noor, 2007; Armstrong, 2004; Dhamayanti E (2017)).

All research variables were measured using a five-point Likert scale with a scale of 1 = strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree. The data analysis methods used are percentage description, competency level category scores and Structural Equation Model (SEM) analysis with the Lisrel 8.80 program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Young Entrepreneurs

Young entrepreneurs who become respondents in this study are young entrepreneurs who are independent entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector located in Pontianak City and Kubu Raya Regency as many as 102 respondents. This study uses the criteria of a young age of 18-40 years according to Hurlock in Hutagalung et al (2010) and Zimmerer (2008), namely the age of young entrepreneurs between the ages of 20-40 years.

General characteristics of young entrepreneurs are gender, age, education, experience, training and type of agricultural business.

Table 1: Characteristics of Young Entrepreneurs

Characteristics	Number of people)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Man	98	96
Woman	4	4
Amount	102	100
Age (Years)		
21 – 25	22	22
26 – 30	53	52
31 – 35	27	26
Amount	102	100
Level of education		
JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL	17	17
SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL	42	41
Diploma/Bachelor	41	40
S2	2	2
Amount	102	100
Experience (Years)		
1 – 3	30	29
4 – 6	58	57
7 - 10	14	14
Amount	102	100
Training		
Once	83	81
Never	19	19
Amount	102	100
Type of business		
Farm	22	21
Fishery	7	7
Horticulture	59	58
Food	8	8
Plantation	6	6
Amount	102	100

Source: Primary Data, 2020

Based on the description in Table 1 shows that almost all young business actors are male by 96%. Most of the young entrepreneurs in the agricultural sector aged 26-30 years by 52% and high school education level of 41%. Most of the agricultural business experience is 4 – 6 years by 57%. Most of the young entrepreneurs have attended training by 81% and the type of agricultural business they run is mostly engaged in horticulture by 58%.

Entrepreneurial Competency Level

The level of competence of young entrepreneurs is described in Table 2 below. The competency level of entrepreneurs is divided into 3 categories, namely good, quite good and not good.

Table 2: Level of Competence in Young Entrepreneurs

Variable	Average Score	Competency Level
Opportunity Competence	16	Pretty good
Conceptual Competence	16	Pretty good
Relationship Competence	19	Well
Organizing Competence	19	Well
Commitment Competence	18	Pretty good
Strategic Competence	28	Pretty good
Amount	116	Pretty good

Source: Primary Data, 2020

The variables of Relationship Competence and Organizing Competence are categorized as good entrepreneurial competence levels, which means that these types of competencies are often applied by young entrepreneurs in running their agricultural businesses, while Opportunity Competence, Conceptual Competence, Commitment Competence and Strategic Competence are categorized as fairly good entrepreneurial competencies, meaning that young entrepreneurs quite often apply these types of competencies but do not quite understand. The average score of all entrepreneurial competence variables can be concluded to be included in the category of quite good level.

The Relation of the Types of Entrepreneurial Competencies to Business Success

The relationship of the types of entrepreneurial competencies to the business success of young entrepreneurs was analyzed using the SEM program Lisrel 8.80. Through this model, it can be seen the effect or relationship between the constructs causally. In this study, there are 7 main latent variables, namely Opportunity Competence, Conceptual Competence, Relationship Competence, Organizing Competence, Commitment Competence, Strategic Competence and business performance. Opportunity Competence measures include general awareness, international orientation and market orientation. Measurement of Conceptual Competence includes conceptual thinking, problem analysis, vision and assessment. Measurement of Relationship Competence includes Communication, Negotiation, Networking, Confidence and Cooperation. Measurement of Organizing Competence includes HRM/HRD, Leadership, and Planning and organizing. Measurement of Commitment Competence includes self-management, value clarification and vision. Measurement of Strategic Competence includes learning orientation, management control, results orientation and strategic orientation. Measurement of business success / performance consists of financial and non-financial. At the initial stage, the overall model fit test was carried out. Based on Hooper et al (2008), assessing the size of the model fit by looking at the value of the chi-square test, RMSEA, CFI and RMSR. Based on the chi-square value of 269.95 with a p-value of 0.000, it can be concluded that this model is not good because the chi-square value is large and the p-value 0.05. The RMSEA (Root mean square error of approximation) value is 0.090, indicating a poor fit of the model because it has a value of of 0.08. The CFI (Comparative Fit Index) value of 0.95 is greater than 0.90, meaning that the model shows a good fit. The RMSR (Root mean square residual) value is 0.035, less than 0.050., so the model shows a good fit. Analysis of the measurement model was carried out regarding the relationship between latent variables and manifest variables

(observed variables). The measurement test is carried out by determining the validity and reliability of the indicators in a construct. To test the validity by looking at the standardized loading factor (SLF) 0.50 (Wijanto, 2008). Hair (2010) suggests that the value of SLF 0.5 indicates that convergent validity has been achieved or it is expected that SLF 0.7, so that from the two opinions, if there is a standardized loading factor value smaller than this limit, the related variable can be eliminated. Of the models. The results of the validity test showed that there were 3 indicators, namely: conceptual thinking, networking and organizing had an SLF value of less than 0.5, so the item was deleted and re-validity measurements were carried out and model respecification was carried out. The results of the validity analysis after removing invalid data are shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Validity and Reliability after Respecific

Latent	Indicator Variables	SLF	Error	SLF ²	CR	AVE
Opportunity	General awareness	0.72	0.48	0.18	2.29	0.57
	Internal Orientation	0.86	0.27	0.7396		
	Market orientation	0.68	0.54	0.4624		
	Total	2.26	1.29	1.7204		
Concept	Problem analysis	0.7	0.51	0.49	2.07	0.50
	Vision and Assessment	0.66	0.56	0.4356		
	Total	1.36	1.07	0.9256		
Relationship	Communication	0.75	0.44	0.5625	2.89	0.53
	Negotiation	0.66	0.58	0.4356		
	Persuasiveness	0.76	0.42	0.5776		
	Cooperation	0.74	0.45	0.5476		
	Total	2.91	1.89	2.1233		
Organization	HR	0.81	0.34	0.6561	1.80	0.59
	Leadership	0.73	0.46	0.5329		
	Total	1.54	0.8	1.189		
Commitment	Self-management	0.62	0.61	0.3844	2.57	0.50
	Value Clarification	0.77	0.41	0.5929		
	Vision	0.67	0.55	0.4489		
	Total	2.06	1.57	1.4262		
Strategic	Learning Orientation	0.83	0.31	0.6889	2.89	0.53
	Management Control	0.65	0.57	0.4225		
	Result Orientation	0.75	0.44	0.5625		
	Strategy Orientation	0.66	0.57	0.4356		
	Total	2.89	1.89	2.1095		
Performance	Financial	0.76	0.42	0.5776	2.02	0.50
	Non-Financial	0.63	0.6	0.3969		
	Total	1.39	1.02	0.9745		

Source: Primary Data, 2020

A variable is said to have good validity on the construct or latent variable if the t value of the loading factor is greater than the critical value (or 1.96) and the standardized loading factor 0.50. In the table above, all indicators of each latent variable still meet the requirements because

the loading factor is > 0.60. This means that these indicators have good validity on the construct or latent variable.

Figure 1: Standardized solution

Source: The results of data analysis using SEM Lisrel 8.80

From the results of the reliability test in Table 3 above for each latent variable based on the CR and AVE values, the CR value of 0.70 and the VE value 0.50 means that all latent variables from the CR and AVE values have met or it can be said that the respondent's answer to the question -The questions used to measure each construct or indicator are consistent and the constructs are reliable/reliable. Testing the suitability of the overall model after respisification is shown in table 4 below.

Table 4: Overall Model Suitability Test after Respecific

No	GOF	Cut off Value	Estimate	Information
1	Chi Square/ X^2 p-value	Getting smaller 0.05	164.80 (P = 0.06014)	Well
2	RMSEA	0.08	0.04	Well
3	CFI	0.90	0.97	Well
4	RMSR	0.05	0.031	Well

Source: Primary Data, 2020

After respisification and testing the suitability of the overall model, the results are getting better. Based on table 4 shows that from the criteria for the Chi Square / X^2 value and p-value, RMSEA, CFI and RMSR have good values, it can be concluded that the model used in this study can be used as the basis for analyzing the problems of this study.

Evaluation or analysis of the structural model includes an examination of the significance of the estimated coefficients. Based on the output of the data analysis, the results of the structural equation analysis are shown in Table 5 as follows.

Table 5: Coefficient Value in Structural Equation

Exogenous Variable	t-value	Information	R2
Opportunity Competence	0.40	Not significant	0.76
Conceptual Competence	1.09	Not significant	
Relationship Competence	2.49	Significant	
Organization Competence	2.47	Significant	
Commitment Competence	0.19	Not significant	
Strategic Competence	2.23	Significant	

Source: Primary Data, 2020

The value of R² serves to show how far each independent variable is able to explain the dependent variable. R² value of 76% means that the variation of the business performance variable (Y) can be influenced by Opportunity Competence, Conceptual Competence, Relationship Competence, Organization Competence, Commitment Competence and Strategic Competence.

Figure 2: T-value Structural Model

Source: The results of data analysis using SEM Lisrel 8.80

From the structural equations and Table 5 and Figure 2, it can be explained that the Relationship Competence variable with the standardized Coefficient value is 0.34 and the t-value is 2.49 indicating that the Relationship Competence variable has a positive effect on business performance. If the Relationship Competence variable is increased by 1, the level of business performance is expected to increase by 0.34. This happens based on young entrepreneurs in trying to have the ability to communicate with others effectively, be it with colleagues or with suppliers or consumers. Young entrepreneurs are able to work positively through discussion and sharing problems and can coordinate activities with colleagues, negotiate with other people both suppliers and consumers and are able to understand what other people mean by their words and actions. This can foster comfort, trust and confidence from outside parties, both suppliers and consumers so that business growth can increase.

Based on research by Hasanah et al, (2018), it is stated that entrepreneurial competence improves business performance. In other words, the higher the entrepreneurial competence, the higher the business performance. Entrepreneurial competencies must be owned by an entrepreneur and improved because they are proven to be able to encourage business success, these competencies include the ability to control risk, find and analyze information, communicate, be dynamic, build social networks, have leadership spirit, ability to negotiate, ability to solve problems and be responsible. Organization Competence variable with standardized Coefficient value is 0.50 and t-value 2.47 indicates that Organization Competence variable has a positive effect on business performance. If the Organization Competence variable is increased by 1, the level of business performance is expected to increase by 0.50. This is based on the ability of young entrepreneurs in placing or assigning employees based on their respective abilities, directing their employees to use the resources utilized before business activities begin and leading their employees in carrying out activities in every field of work so that employees are motivated to work better. And work is more focused and well-coordinated so that productivity and sales growth can be achieved. In line with the results of the research, Pamela et al (2016) stated that the higher the technical management and leadership possessed by farmers, the higher the entrepreneurial competence.

Strategic Competence variable with the standardized Coefficient value is 0.85 and the t-value is 2.23 indicating that the Strategic Competence variable has a positive effect on business performance. This means that if the Strategic Competence variable is increased by 1, the level of business performance is expected to increase by 0.85. Young entrepreneurs apply techniques to critically assess their own behavior and admit their weaknesses Learn to overcome lack of knowledge Learn from past successes, mistakes and failures Don't make the same mistakes Motivated to repeat actions that resulted in past success Perform research before proceeding with business investment, Creating a competitive advantage to compete effectively, designing strategies to prepare for "worst-case scenarios" and forecasting trends and changes in the industry.

This result is in line with the research of Pamela et al (2016) that the higher the strategic ability possessed by farmers, the higher the entrepreneurial competence. Based on research by Hasanah et al, (2018), it is stated that entrepreneurial competence improves business performance. In other words, the higher the entrepreneurial competence, the higher the business performance. Entrepreneurial competencies must be owned by an entrepreneur and improved because they are proven to be able to encourage business success, these competencies include the ability to control risk, find and analyze information, communicate, be dynamic, build social networks, have leadership spirit, ability to negotiate, ability to solve problems and be responsible. Xiang Li (2009) also states that there is a significant relationship between entrepreneurial competence and company performance.

Opportunity Competence, Conceptual Competence and Commitment Competence variables have a t-value of less than 1.96 with a positive standardized Coefficient value, which means that it has no effect on the business performance variable.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussion, it can be concluded that the level of entrepreneurial competence in young entrepreneurs is included in the fairly good category. Relationship competence, organizing competence and strategic competence have a significant positive effect. This means that if relationship competence, organizing competence and strategic competence are improved, business performance can increase. The level of entrepreneurial competence that is classified as sufficient needs to get support from various parties so that the level of competence can increase to be good, through mentoring, coaching, counseling and training related to the skills needed to run their business so that they can develop more. Especially skills related to relationship competence, organizing competence and strategic competence which are types of entrepreneurial competencies that have an influence on business success. In addition to mentoring and training, it is necessary to facilitate capital assistance for these business actors so that they have the opportunity to develop their business. The importance of the role of the younger generation in the economic growth of the country and the region as well as the creation of employment in the agricultural sector, the interest and motivation of the younger generation needs to be continuously grown through academic education, training and assistance with educational institutions, the government and others through programs that are carried out continuously.

Reference

- ❖ Ahmad, Noor Hazlina., Ramayah, T., Wilson, C., Kummerow, L., 2010. Is Entrepreneurial Competency and Business Success Relationship Contingent Upon Business Environment? A Study of Malaysian SMEs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*. Vol 16 No 3. pp 182-203
- ❖ Armstrong M. 2004. *Performance Management*. Publisher Monument. Yogyakarta.
- ❖ Dhamayanti, E., Fauzan, R. 2017. Strengthening Entrepreneurial Characteristics and Competencies to Improve MSME Performance. *Matrix: Journal of Management, Business Strategy and Entrepreneurship* Vol. 11, No. 1. 80-91
- ❖ Dirlanudin. 2010. *Entrepreneurial Behavior and Empowerment of Small Entrepreneurs in the Agro Industry (Case in Serang Regency, Banten Province)*; Bogor Agricultural University Postgraduate School Dissertation.
- ❖ Hair, JF Jr., RE Anderson, BJ Babin, and WC Black. 2010. *Multivariate Data Analysis*, 7th Edition. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- ❖ Hasanah, N., Nur Utomo, M., Hamid H. 2018. The Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competence and MSME Performance in Tarakan City. *Management Insight: Scientific Journal of Management*. 13(2). 27-38.
- ❖ Hazlina, N., Wilson, C., and Kummerow, L. 2011. A Cross-Cultural Insight into the Competency-Mix of SME Entrepreneurs in Australia and Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Management Science*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp 33-50
- ❖ Herawaty, 2016. Young entrepreneurs in increasing agricultural development. *Journal of Agrica Ekstensia*. Vol. 10 No. 2. 81-87.
- ❖ Heru Kristianto, R, 2009. *Entrepreneurship Entrepreneurship Management Approach and Practice*, First Edition, Graha Ilmu, Yogyakarta

- ❖ Hooper et al. 2008. Structural Equation Modeling: Guidelines for Determining Model Fit. The Electronic Journal of Business Research, 6(1): 53 – 60. Available at <http://ejbrm.com>
- ❖ Hutagalung, King Bongsu, 2010. Entrepreneurship. USU Press: Medan
- ❖ Kuratko FD, Hogetts MR. 2007. Entrepreneurship: Theory, Process and Practice. Thomson South-Western.7. Canada.
- ❖ Li, Xiang, 2009. Entrepreneurial Competencies as an Entrepreneurial Distinctive: An Examination of the Competency Approach in Defining Entrepreneurs. Dissertations and Theses Collection. Paper 14.
- ❖ Man TWY, Theresa L, KF Chan. 2002. The Competitiveness of Small and Medium Enterprises: A Conceptualization with a focus on Entrepreneurial Competencies. Journal of Business Ventures. 17(2): 123-142
- ❖ Maryati, S. 2015. The Dynamics of Educated Unemployment: Unemployment Challenges towards Demographic Bonuses in Indonesia. Economics. Journal of Economics and Economic Education. Vol.3 No.2. 124 – 136. DOI: 10.22202/economica.2015.v3.i2.249
- ❖ Noor, HF 2007. Managerial Economics. King Grafindo Persada. Jakarta.
- ❖ Pamela, Rachmat Pambudy, and Ratna Winandi. 2016. Entrepreneurship Competence with the Success of Pujon Dairy Farmers, Malang. Indonesian Agribusiness Journal. Vol 4 No 1. 57-66.
- ❖ Praag CM. 2005. Successful Entrepreneurship. Edward Elgar Publishing Limited. United Kingdom (UK).
- ❖ Pramuwari, T. 2018. The Influence of Entrepreneurial Competence on the Performance of Small and Medium Industries (IKM) Wood Crafts in DIY Province. Thesis. IPB. Bogor.
- ❖ Sarwoko, E., Armanu, S., and Hadiwidjojo, D. 2013 Entrepreneurial Characteristics and Competency as Determinants of Business Performance in SMEs. Journal of Business and Management. ISSN: 2278-487X. Volume 7, Issue 3, PP 31-38
- ❖ Soegoto, Soeryanto, Eddy, Entrepreneurship Becoming a Leading Entrepreneur, Jakarta: PT. Elex Media Komutindo Kompas Gramedia, 2009
- ❖ Suryana, Entrepreneurship Tips and Processes towards Success, 3rd Edition, Jakarta: Salemba Empat, 2006.
- ❖ Syaifullah, Chavchay. 2009. The Young Generation Rejects Poverty. Cempaka Putih Publisher. Klaten.
- ❖ Syarif, YES. 2013. Entrepreneurial Competence of Corn Farmers in Lampung Province. Dissertation of the UNS Postgraduate Program. Surakarta. (Unpublished).
- ❖ Wibowo. 2007. Performance Management. Third edition. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Prasada.
- ❖ Wijandi, Soesarsono. (2004). Introduction to Entrepreneurship. Bandung: New Light.
- ❖ Wijanto, SH 2008. Structural Equation Modeling with LISREL 8.80: Concepts and Tutorials. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- ❖ Wu, WW 2009. A Competency-Based Model for the Success of an Entrepreneurial Start-Up. WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics, 6 (6), 279-291.
- ❖ Zimmerer W. Tohmas. Norman M, Scarborough... 2008. Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management. Jakarta: Salemba four. Jakarta.